

Deriving the Quark Masses Series From a Varying Lorentz Manifold – 8T

"Ideas. I never memorize lines." Bobby Fischer

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Abstract

By using the previous paper success correlating the coupling constant series to $8+(1)$ variations, an analysis of the physical nature of mass to be an arbitrary variation of the manifold converging inward. The idea than implies a pattern with $8 - (1)$ variations. Such pattern was found, and yielded a prediction of a fourth family, about 56 times lighter than the total mass of first generation. The framework predicts infinite families with total mass converging to zero. The rate of converging is currently unknown, there are two options. One is with rescaling factor $(1/9)$ the other is without it. Such prediction could intersect with the enigma of invisible mass, and eliminate the question of arbitrary amount of families. Such a prediction than is a major simplification in a theory.

Introduction

The idea, which is followed by the last paper, is that if $8 + (1)$ to generate force and the coupling constant series, and force is extended outward, (short or long ranged) than $8 - (1)$ would be to generate mass, or arbitrary **variations converging inward**. Equipped with this Idea we can search for a mathematical pattern. First, take all the masses, accurate as they can and combine them according to generation:

$$6\frac{1}{3} * 9 = 57 = 50 + 7$$

$$1320 + 87 = 1407 = 1400 + 7$$

$$\frac{177010}{9} = 19,667 = 19,660 + 7$$

Also, notice that

$$50 * 28 = 1400$$

$$1400 * 14 = 19,600$$

(60 MeV Difference – 0.03%)

but

$$28 = 7 * 4$$

$$14 = 7 * 2$$

so to go from first to second:

$$(7 * 4) * 50 + (7)$$

And from second to third

$$(7 * 2) * 1400 + (7)$$

Notice that it is a decreasing by an even factor of two. In addition, if we go from low to high it does not make sense physically, it should be Lagrangian oriented, nature is devising by increasing amount to minimize the arbitrary variations, so if correct we should go from three to one by devising:

$$\frac{19,660 + (7)}{7 * 2} = 1400 + (7)$$

$$\frac{1400 + (7)}{7 * 4} = 50 + (7) * \frac{1}{9}$$

Next, we can predict that **total mass** for fourth to sixth families:

$$\frac{50 + (7)}{7 * 8} * \frac{1}{9} = 0.113 \text{ MeV}$$

$$\frac{0.113}{7 * 16 * 9} = 0.000113 \text{ MeV or } \frac{0.113}{7 * 16} = 0.00100 \text{ MeV}$$

$$\frac{0.000113}{7 * 32 * 9} = 5.95 * 10^{-8} \text{ MeV or } \frac{0.00100}{7 * 32} = 0.0000045 \text{ MeV}$$

Summing 4-6 families: 0.113113 or 0.1140 MeV. We can see a converging to the value of the forth which is 55.25-55.69 lighter than first family:

$$\frac{6.3}{0.1131130595} = 55.696 \quad \text{or} \quad \frac{6.3}{0.1140} = 55.26$$

Note that we needed to readjust the scale by the factor of $8 + (1)$ as we manipulated the data, in a search for a pattern. Adjust it in the third family, by Multiplication and in the first and by division. The following reason, T-B family has much more mass, thus much more arbitrary variation converging inward, that might be the reason it has $8 + (1)$ factor in the nominator, and in the first, the arbitrary variations are so small, we need to adjust it in the opposite direction, to increase by $8 + (1)$. Whether in the fifth family and below, additional rescales are needed is unknown, we do include two options, with the $8 + (1)$ or without it. So according to the above reasoning and mathematical notion, one will predict infinite family is forming below the masses of the U-D masses, converging to total value of ≈ 0.113113 Mev as family's below the six are neglected due to little contribution the total sum. So overall, we can write:

$$M_{N+1} = \frac{M_N + (7)}{7 * \prod_{E=1}^r N_{E+1}} * \frac{1}{9} \quad (1.3)$$

$$M_{N+1} = \frac{M_N + (7)}{7 * \prod_{E=1}^r N_{E+1}} \quad (1.31)$$

$$N_{E+1} = 2 * N_E$$

$$N_E = 2E; E \geq 1$$

is a function for even amount of variations. N_E

Overview of ideas

Mass is a variation of the manifold converging inward. Just like force but opposite in direction. Nature is eliminating the arbitrary amount of variations by devising in increasing amounts. That prediction is the rule of dark matter in our theory. It suits the fact that very quickly the families total is converging to zero. The rate in which the conserving to zero is made is unknown. The theory provides two options. First, with the rescaling factor to each family and second option without it. Rescaling only Once. Both options agree on the value of the total mass of the fourth, which is about 56 Times lighter than first.

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As we combined the net masses of the two elements, the value should be again, decomposed to the two separate elements. There are an infinite variety of families whose mass is decreasing, thus below first generation of quarks, this could agree with so-called, dark matter. Cosmologists to decide whether the mass values predicted agree with the data.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)

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